

THE PASTORAL COUNSELLORS

JOURNAL *of* **NIGERIAN ASSOCIATION OF PASTORAL COUNSELLORS**

In collaboration with
Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies
and
Department of Guidance and Counselling
LEAD CITY UNIVERSITY, IBADAN, NIGERIA

VOL. 3. MAY 2024

ISSN: PRINT 2971-5199 ONLINE 2971-5202

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Strategies for Promoting Marital Cohesion and National Security in Nigeria

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Abstract

Challenges are inevitable either in micro or macro environments. Marriage is the foundational relationship for all of society, therefore, all other relationships in society stem from the father-mother relationship, and these other relationships thrive most if that father-mother relationship is simultaneously a close and closed husband- wife relationship. Good marriages are the bedrock of strong societies, for they are the foundations of strong families. Marriage contains the five basic institutions, all the basic tasks of society: family, church, school, marketplace and government. These fundamental tasks, if well done in unity between father and mother, make for a very good marriage and peaceful co-existence in the society and nation at large. Within a family built on such a marriage, the child gradually learns to value and perform these five fundamental tasks of every competent adult and of every functional society. Marital cohesion refers to the degree of connectedness, togetherness, and emotional bonding between marital partners. Cohesion in marriages is related to positive relationship qualities, including greater relationship satisfaction and lower hostility between partners. Also, marital cohesion is positively related to individual well-being, such as higher levels of self-esteem. Moreover, national security is commonly used to mean safety from danger and protection from internal, external attack or infiltration. This usage is tied on the apron string of defense and security forces. The cold war era gave the highest currency to the conventional security doctrine that rested on the assumption that only a strong military can effectively deter attacks and threats of force (Chris, 1997). On the contrary, (John, 1991) conceives security in terms of arms, armaments, and military personnel. He posits that security is the relative freedom from harmful threats. In the post-cold war period, the concept of security has attracted a new thinking by contemporary scholars who condemned the militaristic thought of security insisting on the concepts of rehabilitation, transformation and expansion. This study focused on providing strategies to promote marital cohesion and national security.

Keywords: Strategies, marital cohesion, national security, Nigeria

Introduction

Marriage is a globally accepted practice and it means different things to different people even among the scholars. Its understanding varies in every context based on the social and religious

practices of the society. Historically marriage is God's idea and an institution established by Him. Marriage is seen as a social institution as there are rules, rights and responsibilities surrounding marriage because it is seen as the stabilizing force within the societies (Seccombe, 2008). Marriage is one of the most important institutions affecting people's life and well-being. Marital institutions regulate sexual relations and encourage commitment among spouses. This commitment has positive effects, for instance on spouses' health and their earnings on the labor market (Stutxer & Frey, 2005). Marriage and family sociologically signify the stage of greater social advancement. It is indicative of man's entry into the world of emotion and feeling, harmony and culture (Mondal, 2014). Hence, marriage provides an adventure playground for couples and their ability to adjust paves the way for a successful marriage. Marriage has been defined as an institution which creates new social relationships and reciprocal rights among the spouses. As a personal relationship, marriage is deeply meaningful to the individuals involved although "meaningful" is conceptualized differently within social, historical and cultural contexts.

Marriage is not the outcome of a human pervert; it is the outcome of a divine arrangement. God has specifications for the marriage correlation. To attempt to build a marriage without following God's mandate is to invite failure. However, man today is interfering with God's intention and purpose for marriage in so many ways. Until marriage is understood from God's point of view, many marriages will not fulfill its purpose and will eventually experience break-down. If the factors responsible for the rapid and high rate of break-down of marriage and its effects on society are understood by couples, many marriages will be saved.

Challenges in marriage have been perceived as misunderstanding between a man and a woman that can lead to separation, dissolution or divorce of their marriage. Different factors that vary from threat from in-laws, sexual intercourse, delay in child bearing, environmental factors, finance, infidelity and the like are responsible for marital challenges. The reasons for marrying are threefold: fidelity, procreation, and the fulfilling of a sacred obligation. If one did not have the spiritual strength or the economic resources to commit oneself to a fully devout life of celibacy, one could still choose faithfulness and a contained concupiscence. This was the next best thing to celibacy, and a proper and fitting gift of one's self to God. Good marriages are the bedrock of strong societies, for they are the foundations of strong families. The general social survey showed that adults who grew up living with both biological parents experience higher levels of marital happiness. As life expectancy of married persons has increased significantly, divorce rates have skyrocketed since the Victorian era to a new plateau, where almost half of all marriages are expected to end in divorce (Gregorio, 2013: 48-50). Hence, this paper proffers different strategies to curb marital challenges/concerns for cohesion and national security.

Meaning of Marital Challenges

Challenges are a natural phenomenon and it is inevitable in human relationships. It occurs in marriage, family, ministry, communities and organizations. From the Bible point of view, marriage has been grappling with this problem of conflict. The present state of homes depends on the number of challenges it had experienced in the past. In recent times we have witnessed the greatest proliferation of marriages in challenges. It is not possible to rule out conflict in human relationships and the family being an organization where people of different backgrounds,

cultures and languages come together as husband and wife. The two most common responses to challenges are to ignore it and let it go away or handle it badly. All managed challenges on the other hand are good for our marriages (Imobighe, 2003: 17-19).

Marital challenges are perceived as disagreement between couples from the fact that they differ in status, goals or perception. In other words, it is argued that challenges are the opposite of cooperation. This is so because marital challenges imply a process whereby couples see their interests as mutually incompatible, whereas in co-operative processes the parties see their interest as mutually supportive. "Conflict" could replace "Challenges" because a family in conflict is also a family facing challenges. Challenges connotes to "strike together" whenever two or more people pursue mutually exclusive goods or whenever one person's needs collide with another, challenges result (Odukoya, 2012: 105-107). Challenges are indispensable in human society, it occurs between two or more persons, families, marriages and communities, church, government and organization. Marital challenges have the strength to retard progress, growth, development and unity in the society. Marital challenges also mean deep disagreement between husband and wife that could lead to dissolution, separation or collapse of marriage. It is recognized as a struggle or contest between people with opposing needs, ideas, beliefs, values or goals. Incompatibility in marital challenges could bring about individual needs, interests, values, objectives and aims (Amadi-Nche, 2018: 1, 3).

Causes of Marital Challenges in Nigeria

Marital concerns could originate from different sources, some of which could be psychological or psychosomatic in nature. It is retorted that more and more marriages run into marital challenges and eventually pack up because one partner has a borderline personality disorder such as narcissist, antisocial, psychopathic personality disorders (Edward, 1974: 80-82). The underlisted are some of the most prominent causes of marital challenges in Nigeria:

Couple's Incompatibility: Incompatibility has been one of the major causes of marital challenges amidst husband and wife, and this has been generating a lot of issues in the public. To solve this problem, husband and wife should ensure their compatibility before engaging or involving themselves in any marital matters or unending marital journey. This will help to reduce the high rate of divorce caused by this factor and also a tool for cohesion in our society.

Sexual Dissatisfaction: Poor sexual-satisfaction on the part of a married partner may spice up marital challenges in the union if not properly and timely detected and managed. It could lead to extramarital sexual affairs, a situation that on its own leads to disaffection and distrust among couples. When either of the parties is not sexually satisfied, there is the tendency for such to lead to marital challenges among the couple. Oftentimes such predicament tends to be difficult to overcome and manage among the couple and escalate to become unresolved marital challenges that could lead to dissolution or breakage of the home (Wheeler-Reed 50, 51). Sexual dissatisfaction may be as a result of couple mis-orientation about sex, hatred for sex, weak erection by the husband, lack of sexual interest by the wife, stress from both partners or due to fatigue or strenuous office work. If the aforementioned factors are not well managed by the couple, it will lead to marital dishonesty, insecurity, dissatisfactions at all levels and disunity

among the couple. In essence, husband and wife are expected to find a solution to their sexual dissatisfaction which may demand medical attention or special treatment or special counselling.

Problems Emanating from In-Laws, Friends and Relatives: Some men/women often quarrel with spouses whose interests are only on the betterment of their own relations. Trends bordering on in-laws, friends, and relatives constitute a point that never seems to get out of style. Experiences over years and across many cultures and climes have shown that mothers-in-law are culprits for many family challenges. Couples should learn how to put in-laws, relatives and friends in their proper place, outside the sanity of their homes.

Disrespect among Couples: Mutual respect for one's spouse is critical for marital union sustenance and lack of it is a challenging factor capable of rocking even the strongest marital foundation of hitherto blissful homes. Respect and love are reciprocal variables in every marital union and as such, a spouse owes it an obligation to respect and love his/her marriage partner, failure which fans the embers of marital discord and discontent (Keil 45, 46).

Financial Difficulties: Money is one area where marriages are tested today without exception. Whether you are rich or poor, educated or uneducated, you will have to deal with the financial demon that is out to break the home. For the man that refuses to work or that is finding it difficult to get a well-paying job, to the wife that earns much more than the husband, to a spouse that won't cut coat according to pocket size, to a family carrying too much financial responsibilities from relatives and the ones that have poor financial planning skills. Men turn to crime to satisfy an insatiable wife's financial demand. Couples go into rituals with their children as sacrifice just for a little more money. All these end up destroying the family more at the end. In solving these problems they should have a saving culture and in addition think of a small business to do that would guarantee a daily income would do wonders to the happiness experienced in the home (Crossby 85-88).

Globalization: Globalization has failed the family in larger measure. It has eroded strong family values and replaced it with commercialized relationships, thereby inflicting a heavy blow in the marriage institution worldly. The world has become a global village. It has not only made the world smaller, it has also made it independent. The dissolution caused by global trends does not only affect the family economically but also morally, religiously, socially and psychologically (Falako, Francis 326, 327).

Strategies for Promoting Marital Cohesion

Strategy is a system of finding, formulating, and developing a doctrine that will ensure long-term success if followed faithfully. Strategy generally involves setting goals and priorities, determining actions to achieve the goals, and mobilizing resources to execute the actions. Strategy describes how the ends (goals) will be achieved by the means (resources). Marital challenges are not bad or unnatural, it is the way couples handle it that determines its impact on marriage relationship. Marital challenges can destroy or strengthen a marriage while a successful marriage is one in which the couple resolved their differences either openly, secretly, constructively or without any bias for cohesion in the immediate society and national security. Marital challenges are detrimental to the marriage union because it becomes a means to attack, destroy, damage and wound others.

The following are some of the strategies to promote marital cohesion:

Couple's Commitment: Husband and wife should be committed to preserving their marital covenant. They should work out their differences within the context of a loving and irrevocable commitment to their marital covenants and vows. Couples should be determined not to let anything interrupt their marital affairs. They are expected to be open-minded in their discussions and manage their individual differences. Couples are to remain committed to their marital covenants and vows in order to do away with arguments that could generate into hostile, quarreling and confrontations. (Melgosa 77).

Control over Aggression: Husband and wife should not allow their anger to become uncontrollable. Uncontrolled anger among couples becomes a deadly weapon which couples should do away with. Inability to control one's anger could gash either of the couples and become ugly nature by retailing with similar outburst of rancor. Aggressive words can easily break inner peace and confess marriage covenant between husband and wife. Transfer aggression will worsen the situation and as such couples should do away with such and exercise control over their aggression whenever they are angry.

Forgiveness: Couple should have total willingness to forgive and forget. Marital challenges among couples should be handled in a controlled and natural way. It is important for couples to do away with pride, abusive language, irrational accusations and cutting remarks; as such behaviour awakens ugly side of husband and wife in marriage.

Spiritual, Mental and Emotional Unity of the Couples: This comes when husband and wife live in harmony and agreement. Couples should have at least some common values, goals and interests. Culture and language encourage mental and emotional unity between husband and wife. This kind of unity meets people's need for companionship, cohesion, acceptance and value as human beings. Every human being desire to be wanted, loved and appreciated by someone.

Accommodating: Individual couples should seek to meet the needs of others at their own expense. They are not very assertive but are highly cooperative. Accommodating each other will not only help couples to live harmonious life but help them to avoid the opportunity of keeping records of wrong doings which may fuel marital challenges in their homes. Accommodating each other will help a couple to appreciate each other, bring out the best from each other and avail them the opportunity to develop themselves to a higher position and level in life.

National Security

National security is directed at having a reliable, strong and viable state that is free from threat internally and externally which is targeted at peace and tranquility of the state. Bolu-steve and Esere (2017) asserts that security means protection from hidden and harmful disruptions in the partners of daily life in home, offices or communities security, must be related to the presence of peace, absence of crisis, threats to human injury among others. However, Babangida (2012) views National Security as "The physical protection and defense of our citizens and our territorial integrity, of which it is a part, but also the promotion of the economic wellbeing and prosperity of Nigeria in a safe and secure environment that promotes the attainment of our national interests and those of our foreign partners. To Ebeh (2015) national security is more than territorial defense and should focus on the "physical, social and psychological equality of life of the society and its

members both in the domestic setting and within the large regional and global system". For workable understanding of national security, especially when referring to a nation-state, Security means likelihood of survival; it means confidence in the maintenance of state boundaries and the preservation of its territorial, ideological and cultural integrity (George & Ukpog, 2013). It has been observed that there have been no generally and universally accepted conception of national security but it is more than the military aspect, it should encompass all facets of national life in preservation of its values (Otto & Ukpere, 2012). Looking at national security from this perspective we can deduce that marital concerns in our societies will continue to pose a challenge to Nigeria's security and development if not curbed.

Impact of Marital Cohesion on National Security in Nigeria

Marital concerns may have had some deleterious consequences on couples, their children and the society at large. Available literature revealed that social vices and crimes may become the order of the day as delinquent children from crisis-ridden or broken homes ultimately graduate into an irresponsible adult population. The adolescence is a stage at which human beings are highly emotionally unbalanced, character formation not yet stabilized and as such people can always tilt to either side of the scale at the slightest pressure. This is the singular reason why robbery, gangs, kidnap and assassination squads, and prostitution are mostly populated by people in their adolescence and early adulthood. Living with their parents did not offer them the opportunity to develop as good citizens as agents of cohesion and national security with good scales of conscience.

Marital challenge is a serious public health problem and it has both short and long term negative physical and psychological effects on health and wellbeing of Nigerians couples, it constitutes security problems that can endanger the peaceful co-existence of the society and country, in the same manner conflict and insecurity can be very havoc to the sustainable development of the country.

Conclusion

Marital challenges are an essential creative element in human relations, it is the means of change and the means by which our social values of welfare, security, justice and opportunities for personal development can be achieved. In other words, marital challenges are an inescapable part of our daily lives, an inevitable result of our highly complex, competitive and often litigious societies. The paper identifies strategies to curb marital concerns/challenges in Nigeria as a whole; Couple's commitment, control over aggression, forgiveness, spiritual/mental and emotional unity of the couple, setting clear boundaries expectations, establishment of a healthy communication patterns, showing genuine love, seeking professional help such as couples counselling and prioritizing self-care and personal growth.

Recommendations

1. The paper recommends that there is need for more training for couples or those who are coming into marriage to develop more endurance towards each other and seek for marriage counselling.

2. Couples are to jointly combat their marital challenges through prayer, mutual understanding and agreement.
3. Since challenges are inevitable in human society, couples are enjoined to define their marital challenges, and adopt the researcher's strategies accordingly.
4. More talks on husband's materials and wife's materials for the younger ones coming behind for peaceful togetherness in our society and for a secured nation.
5. In addition to the above, this work concludes that God is the harbinger of marriage and that no marriage is exempted from marital challenges, however, strict adherence to all these aforementioned strategies surely promotes marital cohesion in Nigeria.

References

- Amadi-Nche, Church - Hill. *Fundamentals of Conflicts*. Crowther, 2018.
- Association of Nigeria (CASSON) held at the International conference centre, Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun, State between 27th & 31st August, 2012.
- Babangida M.A.: The search for National security in Nigeria: challenges and prospects. <http://www.Nigeria.gov.ng/articles>, 2012.
- Bolu-steve, F. N. & Esere, M. O.: Strategies for managing deviant behaviour among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities & Social Science*. 9(1) 2017.
- Crossby, M. A. *Communication and Conflict in Marriage and Family*. NewYork, 1985.
- Diaman. S. *Handling Family Crisis*,
(<http://www.savemymarriagetoday.com/articles/manag.download21/11/2010>).
- Ebeh J.: National security and National Development: A critique. *International Journal of Acts and Humanities (IJAH)*. 4(2) 14, 2015.
- Edward, Smith. *Why Marriage?* Standard, 1974.
- Falako, Francis. *Biblical Studies and Socio-Political Issues in the Nigerian Context*. Concept, 2017.
- Fatusi A.O, & Blum R.B.: Adolescent health in an international context: the challenge of sexual and reproductive Health in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Adolesc Med State Art Rev*. [Google Scholar]. Retrieved 10-10-2020.
- George, I. N. & Ukpong, D.E.: Contemporary social problems in Nigeria and its impact on national development: implication for guidance and counselling services. *Journal of Educational and Social Research* Vol. 3 (2) 2013.
- Gregorio, Robert. "The Bond Made Holy: A History of Christian Marriage." Spring, 1984.
- Igbo, H.I & Ikpa, I.: Causes, effects and ways of curbing youth restiveness in Nigeria: Implications for Counselling. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(6), 131-137, 2013.
- Iliyasu, Z, Abubakar I. S, Aliyu M. H, Galadanci H. S, & Salihu H. M.: Prevalence and correlates of gender-based violence among female university students in Northern Nigeria. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*. 15(3):111- 119, 2019.
- Imobighe, Thomas A. *Civil Society and Ethnic Conflict Management*. Spectrum, 2003.
- Iwuama B.C. & Ekwe A.O.: Counselling strategies for addressing military and social restiveness in Nigeria. A Paper Presented at the International Conference of the Counselling. 2012.
- Keil C. F. *Commentary on the OT: The Pentateuch*. Vol. 1, Eerdmann, 1980.
- Melgosa, J. *New Life Style: To Couple and Enjoying a Stable Lifelong Relationship*. Madrid, 2005.
- Odukoya, Bayo Samuel. *Church Management and Administration*. May University, 2008.
- Otto and Ukpere.: National security and development in Nigeria. *African journal of business management*. D01:10'5897/AJBM12.155, 2012.

Seecombe, Stutxer & Frey, Mondal. Marital challenges and Adjustment. Journal of the Dept. of Educational Foundations, Uni. Of P/Harcourt, Nigeria. Pg. 92-101. Vol. 5, No 3, 2020.

Seun, O.: Marital Crisis and Divorce; The Reasons all Modern Remedies are Ineffective.
<http://www.savemymarriagetoday.com/articles/manage>

Weaver A; What are the main causes of a marriage crisis? <http://www.premaritalonline.com>

Wheeler-Reed, David. Regulating Sex in the Roman Empire. London, 2017